

IMPROVED SHIP'S NAVIGATION ACCURACY THROUGH PRECISE DATA RECONSTRUCTION

Steven J. Dunham and Jules Kriegsmann

Naval Air Development Center
Warminster, PA 18974-5000

ABSTRACT

A high accuracy post-time navigation data reconstruction technique has been developed for bathymetric survey ships. The ship's navigation system integrates Satellite, LORAN-C, Inertial Navigation, Doppler and Electro-Magnetic Logs and Gyrocompass data. It has been necessary, for some areas, to develop post-time processing algorithms to alleviate position and velocity accuracy degradation arising from infrequent satellite fixes and limited availability of LORAN-C coverage. Enhancement was achieved utilizing log velocity data to detect high frequency inertial navigation Schuler errors. Implementation was achieved by expanding an operational 15-state Kalman smoothing algorithm, incorporating position error measurements only, to a 23-state system which included log velocity measurements.

INTRODUCTION

The Naval Air Development Center has developed a precision integrated navigation system to generate specialized navigation charts aboard various survey ships. The integrated navigation system develops ship's positional data to serve as the horizontal dimensioning reference necessary to complete the specialized charts. The integrated navigation system also develops ship's velocity data to support high accuracy satellite fix computations and ship's attitude data to compensate the transmitted and received sonar data for ship's roll, pitch, and yaw motions.

The main navigation computer develops Best Present Position (BPP) data in real time by combining all available navigation data resources. To achieve the highest accuracy determination of ship's position and velocity, the navigation data is reprocessed in post-time. A series of data reprocessing programs implemented on a dedicated off-line computer system edits, reformats, combines and filters the real-time navigational data. This post-time navigational data refinement process implements a Kalman Smoothing algorithm, which utilizes all of the various data resources available at any given time to derive the highest quality position and velocity data for final product development.

The new post-time processing system has been installed aboard two survey ships, and has demonstrated accuracy enhancements, over what was previously available, in the order of 30% in position and 40% in velocity for survey data devoid of GPS and LORAN measurements. For survey areas where large gravity anomalies are present even larger improvements are possible.

INTEGRATED NAVIGATION SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

A simplified block diagram of the navigation system is shown in Figure 1. The integrated navigation system develops, processes, and records ship's position (in terms of latitude and longitude) and velocity data correlated with time. The sonar system collects time correlated depth data. The integrated system develops real-time bottom contour displays to monitor performance of the navigation system and sonar system data acquisition process. Final product charts are developed utilizing post-time refined navigational data in conjunction with the time correlated depth data.

Figure 1. INTEGRATED NAVIGATION SYSTEM

The Navigation System employs five main subsystem components to support the navigational data acquisition process and BPP computations at the main navigation computer. An automatic ship's track keeping system steers the ship to prescribed survey tracks utilizing BPP derived heading corrections. The primary position reference is derived from the Satellite Navigation System which is currently capable of supplying high accuracy Transit Satellite fixes as well as high accuracy Global Positioning System (GPS) satellite fixes. The Transit Satellite fix data, also referred to herein, as NAVSAT fix data, is nominally available every two hours, depending on the latitude of operation, whereas GPS fixes are available continuously for time spans of various lengths up to a total of 8 to 12 hours per day. GPS fix availability is also dependent on the geographical area of operation due to the limited

number of GPS satellites currently in operation. Ship's Inertial Navigation Systems (SINS) are available to provide continuous position and velocity data. SINS Systems yield excellent high frequency performance and are used to filter out any possible noise contamination present in the GPS data. SINS also serves as the primary source of velocity data to support Transit Satellite fix computations. LORAN-C Receivers supply time difference data in either the conventional hyperbolic mode or in the primary range-range mode for development of continuous highly repeatable LORAN positions when the ship is operating in a LORAN coverage area. LORAN positional data can contain biases, slowly varying errors due to changing uncompensated overland propagation anomalies as well as high frequency noise. Biases and slowly varying errors in the LORAN position are removed using satellite fix data. High frequency LORAN errors are removed by filtering the LORAN solution with SINS, as is done for the GPS data, due to the excellent high frequency characteristics of SINS. Navigation outside of GPS coverage windows and in areas not supported by LORAN-C coverage is accomplished by utilizing discrete Transit Satellite fixes to remove the 24-hour error contamination present in SINS data. As a backup to SINS, dead reckoned (DR) position is derived utilizing log velocity data from two electromagnetic logs (EM Logs) and a Doppler sonar log in conjunction with Gyrocompass heading data. DR position, like SINS position, also demonstrates good high frequency characteristics and serves as a viable backup to SINS for filtering LORAN-C and GPS high frequency noise. Dead Reckon navigation, when supported only with Transit Satellites, in the absence of GPS fixes and LORAN-C data, is used only for transit purposes due to the inherent accuracy limitations.

A precise Time and Frequency System, utilizing two Cesium Beam Frequency Standards, provides the precise timing signals to the LORAN Receivers for range-range LORAN navigation and to the Satellite Navigation System for Transit Satellite and 2-satellite GPS navigation. The Time and Frequency System also provides GMT data to the Navigation Computer and Sonar System so that all data collected will be time synchronized.

POST-TIME PROCESSING

To produce final product navigation data with the highest accuracy possible, the real-time navigation data col-

lected and recorded on magnetic tape is post-time reprocessed with a dedicated navigation data refinement computer system. This computer system is composed of a 16-bit mini-computer, disc drive for rapid access mass storage, four 9-track magnetic tape drives for storage and input and output medium, I/O writer for operator control and a large beltbed plotter to generate various intermediate analytical plots and to generate final form reconstructed ship's track plots and specialized charts.

The software used to accomplish the post-time navigational data refinement and final chart production is divided into three functional categories of programs: preprocessor programs, processor programs, and post-processor programs. The navigation data refinement is accomplished by eleven preprocessor and three processor programs, as illustrated in Figure 2, the heart of which is the Ship's Track Estimation Program (STEP) which implements a Kalman smoothing algorithm.

Eleven preprocessor programs systematically edit and reformat the raw (real-time) navigation data to produce an edited data file for input to the STEP Kalman smoother program. Essentially, it is the job of the preprocessor to ensure that the raw data input to the Kalman smoother contains only those errors which are modeled in the smoothing algorithm. The navigation post-time processing is divided into SINS referenced data-sets or Dead Reckon (DR) referenced data-sets, which are treated separately. This report will address the SINS data-sets only. The raw data file prepared for the Kalman smoother is composed of time indexed mode, control data, resets, 1-minute samples of SINS position and velocity data, and measurements of the SINS errors, herein referred to as divergence data. The divergence data is composed of 3-minute samples of GPS/SINS position divergences, NAVSAT/SINS position divergences, LORAN/SINS (range-range or hyperbolic) position divergences, LORAN/SINS range divergences and LOG/SINS velocity divergences. When available, during the raw data acquisition process, GPS and LORAN position data are recorded at 1-minute intervals and Log velocity data is recorded at 10-second intervals. To produce divergence data of acceptable quality and yet conform to system dynamic requirements, 3-minute mean divergences are formed from the 1-minute position and 10-second velocity samples. NAVSAT fix frequency varies from 20 minutes to 6 hours depending on the geographical area of operation.

Figure 2. NAVIGATION DATA REFINEMENT PROCESS

PREPROCESSING

Initial preprocessing starts with time anomaly testing of the raw navigation data records from the input field navigation data tape. Manual intervention is permitted to correct or delete time recording problems to ensure a continuous or at least controlled flow of 1-minute raw navigation data records. The next stage of the initial preprocessing extracts data from magnetic tape and prepares disc files to serve as the rapid access data source for the succeeding stages of data editing. Initial preprocessing also includes development of required SINS and LORAN reset data.

Preprocessing then continues with statistical editing of the base reference SINS position and velocity data. Data editing results are stored in a data validity word for each 1-minute navigation data record. Specific bits of the validity words are set to 1 or 0 to indicate valid or invalid data. 10-second samples of SINS and LOG velocity data are statistically edited with a standard deviation test to reject data outside the normal distribution to form 3-minute mean LOG/SINS velocity divergences of usable quality. Data samples not meeting specific reasonableness criteria are tagged invalid and will not be used for further processing. 1-minute samples of GPS position and velocity data are similarly statistically processed and edited to form 3-minute mean GPS/SINS position divergences which are also individually tagged valid or invalid as the editing process indicates.

The discrete NAVSAT (Transit Satellite) fixes are tested for reasonableness with respect to BPP with tolerance limits which are variable and are based on various figure-of-merit parameters which are determined and recorded during the real-time fix data acquisition process. Again valid NAVSAT/SINS position divergences are identified with validity words depending on results of the automatic editing process. 1-minute samples of range-range or hyperbolic LORAN position divergences are edited for noise content with respect to the 3-minute mean. Single Range LORAN/SINS range divergence are also formed and then edited for noise content with respect to the 3-minute mean. Again valid data is distinguished from invalid data by storing the editing results in the data validity words. LORAN data processing also includes 10-microsecond jump processing to account for any such jump occurrences which result from cycle slip based on the 100 KHZ LORAN-C carrier frequency. Detected LORAN 10-microsecond, or multiple, jumps result in the automatic formation of an equivalent LORAN reset to properly compensate for such datum shifts. Such pseudo-resets enable the smoothing algorithm of the STEP program to continue propagating the LORAN error estimates without having to reinitialize the LORAN error states after such datum shifts.

Upon completion of the data preprocessing, and statistical editing of raw SINS position and velocity data and the available GPS, NAVSAT, LORAN, and LOG divergence data, the programs provide options to plot the various SINS divergence data on a time axis to graphically illustrate the results of the automatic editing of the preprocessing phase. The various divergence data quantities are plotted with different plot symbols and the validity status is indicated with different colors. This graphical display is easy to analyze due to the predictable and recognizable sinusoidal shape of the SINS error propagation. Velocity divergence data are plotted separately from position divergence data. The purpose of these plots is to graphically illustrate the current editing status of the divergence data which will be supplied to the smoother. The key requirement of the preprocessing phase is to ensure that all abnormal divergence data is tagged invalid before the preprocessor data file is prepared for input to the STEP Kalman smoother program. The

preprocessor programs provide a full range of options for manual overrides to change the validity status for any data quantity by individual record or by blocks of records to ensure that only valid data is made available to the STEP program for the smoothing process.

SMOOTHING PROCESS

The latest version of the processor STEP program implements a 23-state suboptimal Kalman smoothing algorithm to process SINS error measurements (divergence data) obtained from the GPS, NAVSAT, LORAN, and LOG measurement systems. The Kalman smoother is essentially two Kalman filters, one to forward filter the error estimates and the second to reverse smooth the error estimates. Final smooth position and velocity data are then formed by correcting the raw SINS position and velocity data with the smooth error estimates. A graphical analysis program is used to evaluate the quality of the navigation data refinement process. A file merge program is then used to produce the final navigation data product by integrating consecutive smoothed navigation datasets. The initial design and development of this navigation refinement system utilizing a 15-state suboptimal Kalman smoothing algorithm was presented in a similar paper for PLANS 80. The principal new accomplishment in the 23-state implementation was to improve system Schuler detection in areas not supported by LORAN-C coverage. Schuler detection enhancement was achieved by implementing 8 additional system states to accommodate the LOG velocity divergence measurements. In addition, the new system incorporated GPS position divergence measurement data. The smoothing algorithm utilizes GPS measurement data to calibrate the LOG system error states which results in enhanced LOG system performance even outside the GPS coverage windows.

The Kalman smoothing process, as shown in Figure 3, is essentially an error processor which utilizes 1-minute samples of SINS position and velocity and 3-minute divergence data, as available. The smoothing algorithm automatically resets and reinitializes applicable measurement system states upon sensing different data availability or configuration conditions. Eight distinct processing configurations are provided for this purpose and reflect the various combinations of available measurement system data, including: GPS and NAVSAT position divergences, range-range and hyperbolic LORAN-C position divergences, single range LORAN-C range divergences and LOG velocity divergences.

Figure 3. KALMAN SMOOTHER BLOCK DIAGRAM

SINS FILTER DESIGN MODEL

A 14-state SINS filter design model, shown in Figure 4 was developed. The model incorporates the SINS system dynamics consisting of north and east 84-minute Schuler loop position and velocity errors and 24-hour earth-rate north and east tilt and Z angle errors. These error states are driven by north, east and Z gyro drift errors modeled as biases and random walks and external north and east vertical deflection error states modeled as first order Markov processes. The new 14-state model incorporates states for north and east Schuler loop damping to more accurately model the actual SINS damping mechanization.

$U_N, U_E, U_Z, U_{\phi}, U_{\theta}, U_{\psi}, U_{\psi_N}, U_{\psi_E}$: WHITE NOISE DRIVING FUNCTIONS
 $\epsilon_N, \epsilon_E, \epsilon_Z$: NORTH, EAST AND Z GYRO DRIFT RATES
 $\delta P_n, \delta P_e, \delta H$: NORTH AND EAST POSITION AND HEADING ERRORS
 ψ_n, ψ_e, ψ_z : NORTH AND EAST TILT AND Z ANGLE ERRORS
 $\epsilon_{\psi_N}, \epsilon_{\psi_E}$: NORTH AND EAST VERTICAL DEFLECTION ERRORS
 $\delta V_n, \delta V_e$: NORTH AND EAST VELOCITY ERRORS
 L, R : LATITUDE AND EARTH RADIUS
 Ω, g, c', c'' : SCALED VALUES OF EARTH RATE, GRAVITY AND DAMPING
 β_{OCN}, β_{OCE} : FEEDBACK COEFFICIENTS
 $\delta V_N, \delta V_E$: NORTH AND EAST DAMPING OUTPUTS
 $\delta V_{REF,N}, \delta V_{REF,E}$: NORTH AND EAST LOG VELOCITY REFERENCE

Figure 4. SINS FILTER DESIGN MODEL

SATELLITE FILTER DESIGN MODEL

Kalman filter models for the GPS and NAVSAT fix measurement errors are represented as white noise, therefore requiring no states. The white noise variance for GPS satellite measurements is a constant reflecting GPS system performance specifications. The NAVSAT fix measurement error model is composed of white noise variance terms based on NAVSAT system performance specifications and satellite elevation angle and reference velocity error dependent terms. For details of the satellite filter design model, see Appendix A.

LOG SYSTEM FILTER DESIGN MODEL

The LOG system filter design model which is composed of 6-states, shown in Figure 5, was developed. The filter model consists of EM Log No. 1 and No. 2 velocity-fore-aft states and Doppler Log north and east velocity error states. The four measurement system error states are modeled as biases and random walks. In addition, two external first order Markov error states are modeled to account for north and east ocean current errors.

U_{OCN}, U_{OCE} : NORTH AND EAST OCEAN CURRENT WHITE NOISE DRIVING FUNCTION
 U_{L1}, U_{L2} : EM LOG 1 AND 2 WHITE NOISE DRIVING FUNCTION
 U_{DN}, U_{DE} : NORTH AND EAST DOPPLER LOG WHITE NOISE DRIVING FUNCTION
 $\delta V_{L1}, \delta V_{L2}$: EM LOG 1 AND 2 VELOCITY ERRORS
 $\delta V_{OCN}, \delta V_{OCE}$: NORTH AND EAST OCEAN CURRENT ERRORS
 $\delta V_{DN}, \delta V_{DE}$: NORTH AND EAST DOPPLER LOG VELOCITY ERRORS
 β_{OCN}, β_{OCE} : NORTH AND EAST FEEDBACK COEFFICIENTS
 $\delta V_{REF,N}, \delta V_{REF,E}$: NORTH AND EAST OUTPUT VELOCITY ERRORS
 H : HEADING

Figure 5. LOG SYSTEM FILTER DESIGN MODEL

LORAN SYSTEM FILTER DESIGN MODEL

A 3-state LORAN filter design model was implemented for hyperbolic and range-range LORAN measurement data. Hyperbolic LORAN utilizes time difference data from 2 slave stations and an associated master station. The hyperbolic LORAN errors are modeled as bias and random walk error states for each of the 3 stations. Range-range LORAN utilizes time difference data from 2 stations relative to a shipboard cesium clock. The range-range LORAN errors are modeled as a bias, a random walk and a random ramp. 3-states are required for this mechanization. See Appendix A for details of the LORAN system error model.

SUMMARY

The initial concept development was motivated by observation of residual Schuler contamination in smoothed navigation data not supported by frequent LORAN-C position data. Power Spectral Density (PSD) comparisons of SINS and LOG velocity data indicated that SINS data exhibited significantly greater energy in the Schuler frequency band. This suggested that LOG data could be used in the post-time processing to recover Schuler errors. After initial system development, verification of the new process was accomplished utilizing post-time processed LORAN supported data-sets (NAVSAT/LORAN/SINS) to serve as the truth reference. The same data-sets were then reprocessed utilizing LOG data but with LORAN data manually deleted (NAVSAT/SINS/LOG). Reduced, but significant Schuler recovery was observed when utilizing LOG data in place of LORAN data. To establish the degree of improvement with the LOG implementation in non-LORAN areas, the same data-sets were again reprocessed with both LORAN and LOG data manually deleted (NAVSAT/SINS). RMS comparisons of NAVSAT/SINS/LOG

and NAVSAT/SINS performance relative to NAVSAT/LORAN/SINS truth reference performance, indicated LOG implementation accuracy improvements in the order of 30% in position and 40% in velocity.

APPENDIX

NAVSAT and LORAN System filter design models, shown in Figures A1, A2, and A3 for completeness, were presented during PLANS 80 in a paper entitled PRECISE RECONSTRUCTION OF SHIP'S POSITION, by Steven J. Dunham and Bernard H. Shostack (Naval Air Development Center, Warminster, PA).

Figure A1. NAVSAT FILTER DESIGN MODEL

$v_{n1}, v_{n2}, v_{e1}, v_{e2}, v_{m1}, v_{m2}, v_m$ = WHITE NOISE
 $PA_{s1b}, PA_{s2b}, PA_{mb}$ = PROPAGATION ANOMALY BIAS ERRORS FOR EACH TRANSMITTING STATION
 PA_{s1}, PA_{s2}, PA_m = PROPAGATION ANOMALY ERRORS FOR EACH TRANSMITTING STATION
 R_{s1}, R_{s2}, R_m = TRANSMITTING STATION RANGES
 P_{s1}, P_{s2}, P_m = POWER OF TRANSMITTING STATIONS

Figure A2. HYPERBOLIC LORAN-C FILTER DESIGN MODEL

$\delta f_{cb}, \delta f_{cb}$ = FREQUENCY STANDARD OFFSET AND BIAS ERRORS
 δf_c = FREQUENCY STANDARD ERROR
 $v_{n1}, v_{n2}, v_{e1}, v_{e2}, v_{m1}, v_{m2}, v_m$ = WHITE NOISE
 R_1, R_2 = TRANSMITTING STATION RANGES
 P_1, P_2 = POWER OF TRANSMITTING STATIONS
 PA_{s1b}, PA_{s2b} = PROPAGATION ANOMALY BIAS ERRORS FOR EACH TRANSMITTING STATION
 PA_{s1}, PA_{s2} = PROPAGATION ANOMALY ERRORS FOR EACH TRANSMITTING STATION

Figure A3. RANGE AND RANGE-RANGE LORAN-C FILTER DESIGN MODEL